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Zakaria Abdiwali Mohamed & Mustafa Ünsalan

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Does AI marketing efforts affect brand loyalty of Gen Z consumers? Mediating role of brand image and brand experience

Zakaria Abdiwali Mohamed^a

^aDepartment of Management, University of Kabridahar, Kabridahar, Ethiopia; ^bDepartment of Management, Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Ankara, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

The integration and adaptation of artificial intelligence (AI) in marketing are continually expanding as technological advancements progress, yet there is a scarcity of research investigating the impact of AI tools, on brand development processes, including brand loyalty. Grounded in the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) theory, this paper investigates the impact of AI-driven marketing efforts on brand loyalty and repurchase intentions among Gen Z consumers in Türkiye. Additionally, the paper investigates the mediating roles of brand image and brand experience. Adopting an exploratory research design, data were collected from 476 young consumers, and PLS-SEM was employed for analysis. The findings indicate that AI marketing efforts (AIME) do not have a significant direct effect on brand loyalty but do influence it indirectly through brand image. Furthermore, brand image significantly impacts brand loyalty, which, in turn, exerts a direct influence on the repurchase intentions of Gen Z consumers. This study makes a significant contribution to the marketing literature by offering deeper insights into the effects of AI marketing efforts on brand loyalty and repurchase intentions. The research enriches theoretical understanding and provides practical implications for marketers aiming to strengthen customer loyalty and encourage repeat purchases.

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1. Introduction

Owing to technological advancements, the integration and application of artificial intelligence in the marketing sector are undergoing consistent expansion (Campbell et al., 2020). The utilization of AI in marketing entails the provision of timely and automated solutions to address customer queries and issues (Martínez-López & Casillas, 2013; Negnevitsky, 2005). AI technology has significantly contributed to the innovation, development, and brand management of business organizations (Cheng & Jiang, 2020). Moreover, AI assumes a key role in enhancing brand loyalty and leading customer relationships. By adopting AI, businesses can establish sustainable customer relationships through alternative means. It has been observed that establishing sustainable customer relationships positively correlates with brand loyalty (Nazir et al., 2023).

The ongoing utilization of AI assistants fosters customer loyalty within brands of a similar nature (Maroufkhani et al., 2022). Artificial intelligence services, including Voice Assistants (VA), are instrumental in the development and reinforcement of brand loyalty (Hasan et al., 2021). From a strategic standpoint, AI marketing endeavors aid business organizations in reaping the advantages and upholding loyalty with their customers (Hasan et al., 2021). The rapid purchase intention of consumers is influenced by AI-enhanced online information. AI-driven marketing initiatives provide consumers with diverse choices and alternatives for the same product, thereby shaping their brand loyalty and influencing their repurchase intentions. Consumers obtain product information from various sources, including friends, family, reviewers, and AI-based recommendations. As a result, AI marketing efforts influence customer

purchasing behavior, brand loyalty and repurchase intention (Kohli et al., 2023). The existing literature on the interaction between AI-based tools and brand loyalty reveals a substantial correlation between these variables (Ibrahim, 2022).

Currently, there is a paucity of research investigating the impact of AI tools, such as interactive voice assistants, on brand development processes, including brand loyalty (Maroufkhani et al., 2022). Other research has explored the impact of AI tools on brand experience (Ho & Chow, 2024; Ifekanandu et al., 2023). As well as AI marketing efforts and the establishment of brand image (Nufer & Muth, 2022). The existing literature suggests that AI marketing efforts significantly influence on brand management, contributing to its improvement and providing organizations with a competitive advantage (Chen et al., 2023; Ibrahim, 2022; Ifekanandu et al., 2023; Maroufkhani et al., 2022). Consequently, this study explores two mediating variables brand image and brand experience to determine whether these factors elucidate the impact of AI marketing initiatives on brand loyalty and consumer repurchase intentions. Furthermore, a prior study on brand loyalty has found that brand experience exerts a positive influence on brand loyalty (Akoglu & Özbek, 2022). and brand image influences consumer loyalty (Durmaz et al., 2018).

While artificial intelligence (AI) is extensively utilized worldwide, there remains a paucity of research examining its role in branding (Ho & Chow, 2024). Cheng and Jiang (2022) emphasize the necessity for additional research into the impact of AI marketing efforts (AIME) on brand loyalty. The existing body of literature on AI and marketing has primarily focused on the impact of AIME in developed countries, with insufficient attention paid to emerging markets (Cheng & Jiang, 2022). Conversely, Ho and Chow (2024) studied the influence of AI marketing efforts on consumer preference of the brand within the banking sector, recommending further exploration across other industries. Although artificial intelligence plays a pivotal role in shaping consumer-brand relationships, there is still a notable gap in thorough and cohesive research concerning its effects on branding (Ho & Chow, 2024). Addressing these gaps, this paper investigates the effect of AI-driven marketing efforts on brand loyalty and repurchase intentions among Generation Z consumers in Türkiye. Ameen et al. (2023) highlight the importance of investigating how Gen Z interacts with new-age technologies across various domains. This paper also observes two mediating variables namely, brand experience and brand image to elucidate the indirect impact of AIME on brand loyalty and repurchase intention. To the researchers' knowledge, no existing research have explored the effect of AI marketing efforts on brand loyalty among Generation Z consumers, considering the role of these intervening variables.

This study is grounded on the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) theory, which is widely applied in the field of AIME and brand development (Ho & Chow, 2024; Nazir et al., 2023). The SOR theory explains the relationship between inputs (Stimuli), process (Organism), and output (Response). Initially, various researches examined the theory, and the findings validated the utility and reliability of the SOR model in accurately understanding the behavior of young consumers (Akin, 2023). In this research, AI marketing efforts function as the stimuli for brand experience and brand image, while brand experience and brand image serve as the organism factors influencing brand loyalty and repurchase intention. In this paper, brand loyalty and intention to repurchase acts as an output (Response). According to Aaker (2012), brand experience contributes to the creation of brand loyalty.

By bridging the observed research gaps, this paper offers several notable contributions to the field. First of all, it rigorously evaluates various models to explore the relationships between AIME, brand loyalty, and repurchase intention, positioning itself as one of the pioneering studies in this area. Secondly, it investigates into the connections between AIME, brand experience, and brand image, offering new insights into these relationships. Thirdly, the study examines the mediating roles of brand image and brand experience in the relationship between AIME, brand loyalty, and repurchase intention, thereby deepening our understanding of the indirect impact of AIME on brand loyalty. These contributions are significant as they not only advance theoretical understanding in the field of AI-driven marketing but also suggest implications for marketers. This study examines the role of AIME in shaping brand-related outcomes such as brand loyalty and repurchase intention. While prior studies have demonstrated the positive impact of AIME on customer engagement and loyalty (Hasan et al., 2021; Kohli et al., 2023;), significant contradictions remain. For instance, some works report direct positive effects of AI tools on brand loyalty (Cheng & Jiang, 2022), while others suggest indirect impacts mediated by variables like

trust or satisfaction (Maroufkhani et al., 2022;) These discrepancies highlight the need to explore how factors like cultural differences, generational attitudes and industry-specific contexts influence outcomes. By uncovering the mediating effects of brand experience and brand image, the study highlights critical factors that can amplify the effectiveness of AI marketing strategies. This nuanced understanding can aid marketers in designing more targeted and impactful campaigns that enhance brand loyalty and encourage repurchase intentions among Generation Z consumers. Furthermore, the study's focus on an emerging market like Türkiye adds valuable context to the global discourse on AI in marketing, emphasizing the need for localized strategies that consider cultural and market-specific nuances. Existing studies predominantly focus on developed markets, leaving a gap in understanding how AIME functions in emerging markets like Türkiye. This study contributes by addressing this gap, using the SOR framework to examine mediating roles of brand image and experience. By focusing on Generation Z, a demographic heavily influenced by digital transformation, the study enriches insights into how AIME can be optimized for this tech-savvy cohort. In summary, this research expands the breadth of AI marketing literature and establishes a basis for future investigations into the intricate dynamics between AI technologies and consumer-brand relationships.

Structurally this paper contains the following sections: the next section provides a review of the literature and the formulation of hypotheses. The second section outlines the study's methodological approach, while the third section focuses on data analysis. The fourth section presents the discussion and conclusions. The fifth and sixth sections outline the implications of the findings and acknowledge the study's limitations, respectively.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

2.1. Literature review

2.1.1. AI marketing efforts

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is defined as the ability of computer systems to execute tasks that require intelligence, such as learning, planning, logical reasoning, critical thinking and solving problems creatively in everyday scenarios (Zhang et al., 2021). The domain of AI involves information technologies that collect and analyze data to generate meaningful insights, which can be utilized for a range of applications (Paschen et al., 2020).

AI marketing efforts are defined by the dimensions of interaction, information, accessibility, customization, and entertainment. Among these, interaction plays a central role especially through the connections that take place between customers and AI brand representatives within digital settings. Similar to human interactions, AI chatbots have revolutionized the traditional one-way purchasing process, transforming it into a bidirectional exchange with online service agents. This transformation has significantly reshaped the landscape of marketing communication (Chung et al., 2020). The next dimension of AIME is information, it relates to a core marketing function of AI chatbots: Delivering information to customers regarding products, services, or the brand. Consumers favor acquiring information through AI tools over other digital platforms, as these tools deliver relevant, well-organized information, thereby enabling individuals to make more informed choices (Brill et al., 2022). The third dimension of AIME, accessibility, signifies to the ability of AI technology to effectively and promptly access and manage customer data. According to Zarouali et al. (2018), this capability has become a vital feature of media that AI chatbots can offer to enhance marketing communications.

Additionally, entertainment serves a crucial function in marketing by delivering engaging and valuable content, enhancing perceived value, and encouraging the use of digital marketing tools (Chung et al., 2020). Much like various social media platforms, AI chatbots are also sought after for their ability to provide entertainment and amusement (Brandtzaeg & Følstad, 2017; Chung et al., 2020). The integration of entertainment into marketing strategies has been shown to be successful in cultivating a favorable brand image, stimulating an intention to repurchase, and increasing brand awareness (Kim & Ko, 2012). Lastly, customization pertains to the ability of AI-powered chatbot marketing to deliver personalized assistance to customers, thereby addressing their individual requirements (Godey et al., 2016). For instance, Gucci employs customized messaging for every customer and develops products that are

tailor-made to suit their preferences (Sangar, 2012). (Bag et al. (2022) highlight that AI-powered recommendation systems, when combined with social media engagement, significantly enhance brand loyalty. Similarly, Chen et al. (2023) demonstrated that AI chatbots' ability to deliver personalized, engaging content strengthens brand relationships, particularly among Gen Z consumers.

2.1.2. Brand loyalty and repurchase intention

Brand loyalty refers to a consumer's consistent preference and selection of a particular brand over competing alternatives, even when there are differences in price (Maroufkhani et al., 2022). It plays a crucial role in enabling firms to expand their customer base and secure an edge over competitors (Nasir, 2005). The concept of repurchase intention pertains to the inclination of consumers to consistently choose a particular brand for their future purchasing decisions (Kim et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2011). Extensive research has demonstrated that post-purchase consumer behavior frequently encompasses positive word-of-mouth promotion and brand loyalty (Shahid et al., 2018). When consumers experience satisfaction with a brand, they exhibit a tendency to repeatedly engage with that brand, thus fostering long-term consumer loyalty (Hussain et al., 2024). Re-purchase intention indicates the future continues purchase of the consumers toward a specific brand or product. Customer satisfaction is positively correlated with customers' intention to repurchase. In the contemporary digital age, consumers largely rely on digital social networks as a primary source of product information, while businesses utilize these platforms to efficiently improve their customer conversion rates (Bag et al., 2022).

2.2. Hypothesis development

2.2.1. AI marketing efforts and brand experience

Brand experience refers to the overall engagement and acquaintance a consumer develops with a brand, encompassing the interaction between products, people, processes, and settings, which trigger cognitive, sensory, emotional and behavioral reactions (Trivedi, 2019). Wasan (2018) depicts brand experience as the consumer's understanding of the entire service interaction, encompassing their emotions and attitudes throughout the decision-making and consumption stages. Few studies have explored the relationship between AIME and customer brand experience (Ho & Chow, 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies play an essential role globally by providing customers with new brand experiences. These technologies enhance customer experiences, thereby strengthening brand-customer relationships (Ho & Chow, 2024). Particularly, the consumer experience is enhanced by technological advancements. This indicates that AI marketing initiatives contribute to the enhancement of customer experiences (Ho & Chow, 2024). Furthermore, the current body of research on AIME and brand experience indicates that AIME affects brand experience (Nguyen et al., 2022) When consumers encounter high-quality information generated by AI, their satisfaction is likely to increase, leading them to continue utilizing the technology due to the favorable experience (Trivedi, 2019). While this study focuses on Türkiye, examining findings from other regions provides valuable context. For instance, studies from East Asia (Ho & Chow, 2024; Ko et al., 2024; Nguyen et al., 2022) reveal that cultural preferences for high customization amplify AIME's impact on brand loyalty and brand preference, whereas Western markets prioritize entertainment and convenience (Brill et al., 2022; Cheng & Jiang, 2022). AI marketing efforts impact customers' brand experiences, brand preferences, and repurchase intentions. Specifically, factors such as information provision, accessibility, and customization significantly shape the brand experience. However, the influence of interaction is not statistically significant (Ho & Chow, 2024). According to SOR theory the AIME are the stimuli of brand development (Ho & Chow, 2024; Nazir et al., 2023). Hence, the study developed this hypothesis.

H1: *AIME information(H1a), accessibility(H1b), customization(H1c) and entertainment(H1d) have positive significant effect on the brand experience and interaction(H1e) have no significant effect on brand experience.*

2.2.2. AI marketing efforts and brand image

Strong brand image contributes to the formation of an enduring brand memory within consumers' minds (Keller et al., 2011). According to Aaker (1991), brand image consists of a collection of ties

connected to a brand in memory, typically in a meaningful manner. Brand image is the beliefs of the consumers toward the brand (Kotler & Armstrong, 1996). Recently, Cheng and Jiang (2022) identified that AIME have a significant impact on customer-brand relationships. That means brand image can be formulated by developing a customer brand relationship. While Kotler and Armstrong (1996) argue that Brand image is the beliefs and relationship of the consumers toward the brand. AI plays crucial role on different brand development activities such as building brand image and maintaining brand loyalty (Teoh & Jin Goh, 2023). Moreover, the literature has identified a substantial impact of AI technologies on the relationship between brands and customers (Nguyen et al., 2022). Considering the SOR theory AI marketing efforts are the stimuli of brand image (Ho & Chow, 2024; Nazir et al., 2023). Hence, the study proposed that

H2: *AIME information(H2a), accessibility(H2b), customization(H2c), entertainment(H2d) and interaction(H2e) have positive significant effect on brand image.*

2.2.3. AI marketing efforts and brand loyalty

Brand loyalty is characterized as a consumer's persistent preference and inclination toward a particular brand, despite the presence of competing alternatives and variations in price (Maroufkhani et al., 2022). It is a crucial factor for companies aiming to expand their business reach and take an advantage over rivals (Nasir, 2005). Nonetheless, there is a limited body of research addressing the effect of AI-based voice assistance technologies on brand loyalty (Maroufkhani et al., 2022). AI technologies, such as Voice Assistants (VAs), are increasingly critical in fostering and establishing brand loyalty. Strategically, AI marketing efforts enable businesses to cultivate and sustain customer loyalty (Hasan et al., 2021). Consumers receive product information from various sources, including friends, family, reviewers, and AI-driven recommendations, thereby influencing their buying behavior, brand loyalty, and repurchase intentions (Kohli et al., 2023). The existing literature highlights a significant association between AI-based tools and brand loyalty (Ibrahim, 2022). According to the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) theory, brand loyalty is a response generated by brand experience and brand image, which serve as the organism influenced by AIME. Consequently, this study proposes that;

H3: *AIME information(H3a), accessibility(H3b), customization(H3c), entertainment(H3d) and interaction(H3e) have significant effect on brand loyalty.*

2.2.4. Brand experience, brand image and brand loyalty

The existing literature indicates a substantial positive impact of brand experience on brand loyalty (Akoglu & Özbek, 2022). Brand experience includes the comprehensive interaction and degree of familiarity that consumers establish with a brand. A brand is deemed successful when it can forge a robust connection with consumers, thereby discouraging them from choosing competing brands. The foundational step in developing this connection is for consumers to engage with the brand (Akoglu & Özbek, 2022). Brakus et al. (2009) describe brand experience as an internal, subjective process that results from a stimulus. This study follows the SOR theory and considers brand experience and brand image as processes that occur after the stimuli of AI marketing efforts. Furthermore, brand experience affects brand loyalty from different perspectives (Brakus et al., 2009). Also, Brakus et al. (2009) argues that consumers prefer brands that provide a favorable brand interaction, resulting in a higher likelihood of repurchase intention for these types of brands. Hence, it is proposed that;

H4: *Brand experience has a positive significant effect on brand loyalty*

Brand image exerts a significant positive influence on brand loyalty (Durmaz et al., 2018). A strong brand image ultimately contributes to the creation of lasting brand memories in consumers' minds (Keller et al., 2011). which in turn fosters brand loyalty. Fostering brand loyalty entails developing and maintaining enduring relationships with consumers. Building brand awareness and developing brand recognition through perceived quality are essential in maintaining these relationships, with loyalty programs also playing a supportive role in this process (Aaker, 2012). Given the positive and significant impact of brand image on brand loyalty (Xu et al., 2022). Hence it is proposed that;

H5: *Brand image has a positive significant effect on brand loyalty.*

2.2.5. Brand loyalty and repurchase intention

Consumers spread the good news about brands that satisfy their needs, which leads to loyalty and repurchase intention of that specific brand (Brakus et al., 2009). This indicates that the consumer will most likely repurchase to that brands and recommend it to the others (Yu et al., 2021). Loyal consumers repeatedly purchase from a specific brand, which increases their intention to repurchase. When customers demonstrate commitment to a brand, they tend to develop loyalty and exhibit recurring purchase behavior (Erciş et al., 2012). Brand loyalty have direct strong effect on repurchase intention (Vazifehdoost & Negahdari, 2018). When a customer finds satisfaction with a product that meets their needs, they are likely to cultivate brand loyalty. This loyalty, in turn, strengthens the likelihood of repurchase (Yu et al., 2021). The existing literature on the connection between brand loyalty and repurchase intention indicates that repurchase intention is contingent upon the extent of consumer loyalty (Erciş et al., 2012; Vazifehdoost & Negahdari, 2018). Therefore, the study proposes the following hypothesis.

H6: *Brand loyalty has a positive significant effect on repurchase intention.*

2.2.6. Brand image and brand experience as a mediators

The effect of AIME on brand image is well-established (Cheng & Jiang, 2022). Furthermore, brand image has been demonstrated to have a positive and significant impact on brand loyalty (Durmaz et al., 2018). According to SOR theory, AI marketing efforts can be regarded as stimuli affecting brand loyalty. In this framework, brand image and brand experience act as intermediaries between AIME and brand loyalty (Ho & Chow, 2024; Nazir et al., 2023). Previous studies have consistently found a significant positive association between brand experience and brand loyalty (Akoglu & Özbek, 2022). It is broadly acknowledged that the initial step toward achieving brand loyalty involves consumers having a significant experience with the brand (Akoglu & Özbek, 2022). Therefore, it is suggested that;

H7a-H7e: *Brand image mediates the relationship between AIME (information, accessibility, customization, entertainment, interaction) and brand loyalty.*

H8a-H8e: *Brand experience mediates the relationship between AIME (information, accessibility, customization, entertainment, interaction) and brand loyalty.*

3. Methodology

The researchers applied exploratory research design to investigate the effect of AIME on brand loyalty and repurchase intention among Gen Z consumers in Türkiye. The generational theory posits that individuals from varying birth date ranges exhibit distinct socio-demographic and behavioral traits (Vitezić & Perić, 2021). Generational theory outlines the attributes and characteristic of individuals within a specific generation. Gen Z, commonly known as 'Zoomers', includes individuals born between 1997 and 2012 and is the generation that follows Generation Y and precedes Generation Alpha (Dimock, 2019). Members of Gen Z exhibit distinct and similar values, traits, lifestyles, characteristics, and behaviors globally, a result of the continually changing environment, which differentiates them from earlier generations. As Gen Z matures into adulthood, they are increasingly engaged in making purchasing decisions and handling personal responsibilities. Born into a digital era, Generation Z has experienced an unparalleled immersion in technology throughout their upbringing. Their lives are intricately intertwined with the internet and technological advancements, which they seek to navigate seamlessly and securely (Priporas et al., 2017). Given their high levels of education, innovation, and digital proficiency, Generation Z is inherently inclined to adopt AI-related innovations more readily and seamlessly compared to other generational cohorts (Self et al., 2019). The study examines brand image and brand experience as intermediary variables in the linkage between AIME and brand loyalty. Data were collected from 476 respondents in Türkiye using an online survey questionnaire. The study focuses on Generation Z because it is assumed that consumers in this generation will act as the first majority of AI adopters in the near future.

The study employed Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) as the analytical method. PLS-SEM was chosen over Covariance-Based SEM (CB-SEM) for several reasons. First, PLS-SEM is

particularly suited for exploratory research, especially when the primary goal is to predict relationships and assess the path coefficients within a complex model. Second, PLS-SEM is robust with smaller sample sizes compared to CB-SEM, and while the current study's sample size of 476 exceeds the recommended thresholds for both approaches, PLS-SEM remains advantageous given the inclusion of multiple constructs and mediating variables in the model (Shmueli et al., 2019). Third, PLS-SEM places fewer restrictions on data distribution and is less sensitive to non-normality, which makes it more appropriate for real-world data that may deviate from strict normality assumptions (Hair et al., 2013). Finally, the method aligns with the study's focus on theory development and prediction, which are central to understanding the dynamics of AIME, brand image, brand experience, brand loyalty, and repurchase intention in the context of Gen Z consumers. By providing a robust framework for analyzing complex relationships and accommodating the study's methodological requirements, PLS-SEM was deemed the most suitable analytical approach.

This study builds upon the insights and methodologies of previous research but addresses several limitations identified in the existing literature. For instance, prior studies often relied on relatively small sample sizes collected via online surveys, such as the 300 valid samples in Ho and Chow (2024) work, which may restrict the generalizability of findings. Similarly, Cheng and Jiang (2022) focused exclusively on the US market, limiting their study's cultural applicability. Nguyen et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of testing conceptual frameworks across different industries and cultural contexts, as the maturity of AI applications varies significantly across countries. Additionally, longitudinal investigations were suggested by Nguyen et al. (2022) as critical for understanding the temporal effects of AI quality on customer experience and long-term relationships. Nazir et al. (2023) highlighted that research often overlooks moderating factors such as brand name and social media star ratings, which could provide deeper insights into consumer behavior. By addressing these methodological and contextual gaps, this study contributes to the literature by focusing on a larger, demographically diverse sample of Gen Z consumers in Türkiye examining cross-cultural dimensions and mediating factors and employing PLS-SEM for robust analysis.

3.1. Measurements

This study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the University of Kabridahar, under registration number (17/03/2024–03/12). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement. Participants were thoroughly informed about the study's objectives, procedures, and their rights, including the right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Written consent ensured that participants fully understood the study and voluntarily agreed to participate, with their confidentiality and autonomy respected throughout the research process. The research utilized a five-point Likert scale. The measurement scales for AIME, including interaction, information, accessibility, customization, and entertainment, were adapted from (Cheng & Jiang, 2022). Similarly, the scales for brand loyalty were drawn from (Cheng & Jiang, 2022), the brand experience scale from (Ho & Chow, 2024), and the brand image scale from (Xu et al., 2022). The repurchase intention scale was also adapted from (Ho & Chow, 2024). [Appendix D](#) provides a summary of the sources from which the instruments and their corresponding items were derived.

A total of 500 questionnaires were administered online, with 476 being completed and returned, yielding a response rate of 95.2%. The questionnaire was distributed through popular social media platforms (Instagram, Twitter/X, and TikTok) where Generation Z users are highly active. Individuals who expressed interest in participating after viewing the survey announcements were contacted directly and provided with the survey link. Once 500 valid requests were received, the researchers limited the distribution to this group to ensure manageability and data quality. Out of these 500 invited participants, 476 completed the questionnaire in full, resulting in a response rate of 95.2%. This high completion rate is attributed to the voluntary nature of participation and the relevance of the research topic to the respondents. Data analysis was performed using SmartPLS 4. The conceptual framework of the study is illustrated in [Figure 1](#), which demonstrates the conceptualization of AIME, brand image, brand experience, brand loyalty, and repurchase intention within the framework of SOR theory. Although repurchase intention is considered a behavioral dimension of brand loyalty (Yu et al., 2021), brand loyalty encompasses both attitudinal (affective commitment) and behavioral (repurchase) aspects. In this study, we

Figure 1. Research model.

conceptualize brand loyalty as a broader construct that influences repurchase intention, allowing us to test the sequential relationship aligned with the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) framework.

4. Data analysis

4.1. Measurement model

The study's variables included the dimensions of artificial intelligence marketing efforts, specifically: accessibility (ACC1 to ACC4), interaction (INT1 to INT3), information (INF1 to INF3), customization (CN1 to CN4), and entertainment (EN1 to EN4). The dependent variables were brand loyalty (BL1 to BL4) and repurchase intention (RI1 to RI5). Brand experience (BE1 to BE5) and brand image (BIM1 to BIM6) served as mediators, influencing the association of AIME and brand loyalty.

The PLS-SEM analysis involved two key components the measurement model, which was used to evaluate the reliability and validity of the constructs, and the structural model. In this study, all item factor loadings were higher than the minimum acceptable level of 0.500, indicating satisfactory reliability. Both Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability were calculated to further evaluate reliability. For all constructs, the values of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability surpassed the recommended threshold of 0.700, demonstrating high construct reliability. Average variance extracted (AVE) was used to assess for convergent validity. All constructs showed a level of convergent validity above the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.500, confirming that the constructs effectively measured their intended concepts. Table 1 provides a summary of the reliability and validity of the constructs.

Discriminant validity was assessed through the Fornell-Larcker criterion and the heterotrait-monotrait ratio. These tests confirmed that the constructs were distinct from one another according to the established criteria. Tables 2 and 3 offer an overview of the Fornell-Larcker criterion and the heterotrait-monotrait ratio results. Furthermore, the correlations between latent variables, as detailed in Table 4, reveals generally significant and positive relationships among all constructs, supporting the conceptual framework. Particularly strong correlations were observed between brand loyalty and both brand image and repurchase intention, reinforcing their interconnected roles in the SOR model. While some AI marketing effort dimensions, such as Information (INF) and Interaction (INT), exhibit high correlations ($r=0.871$), this result is not unexpected given the conceptual proximity of these constructs in digital communication contexts. Both dimensions inherently involve consumer engagement with AI systems, often occurring simultaneously during chatbot or voice assistant interactions. To ensure construct distinctiveness, we conducted thorough discriminant validity assessments using both the Fornell-Larcker criterion and HTMT ratio, all of which confirmed that each construct maintained acceptable discriminant thresholds. Additionally, multicollinearity diagnostics (VIF values ranging from 1.79 to 4.21) indicated no statistical concern. Therefore, while conceptually related, the constructs are empirically distinct and methodologically robust within the model.

Table 1. Reliability and validity analysis.

Construct	Item	Loading	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE
Accessibility	ACC 1	0.846	0.903	0.932	0.774
	ACC 2	0.870			
	ACC 3	0.924			
	ACC 4	0.877			
Interaction	INT 1	0.873	0.833	0.900	0.750
	INT 2	0.884			
	INT 3	0.841			
Information	INF 1	0.898	0.863	0.916	0.785
	INF 2	0.879			
	INF 3	0.880			
Customization	CN 1	0.888	0.914	0.939	0.794
	CN 2	0.881			
	CN 3	0.888			
	CN 4	0.908			
Entertainment	EN 1	0.871	0.911	0.937	0.788
	EN 2	0.889			
	EN 3	0.926			
	EN 4	0.865			
Brand experience	BE 1	0.897	0.923	0.942	0.766
	BE 2	0.872			
	BE 3	0.909			
	BE 4	0.882			
	BE 5	0.813			
Brand image	BIM 1	0.722	0.905	0.927	0.680
	BIM 2	0.818			
	BIM 3	0.874			
	BIM 4	0.874			
	BIM 5	0.803			
	BIM 6	0.847			
Repurchase Intention	RI 1	0.911	0.927	0.948	0.821
	RI 3	0.923			
	RI 4	0.890			
	RI 5	0.900			
	RI 2	0.923			
Brand loyalty	BL 1	0.896	0.912	0.938	0.792
	BL 2	0.920			
	BL 3	0.886			
	BL 4	0.856			

Table 2. Fornell & Larcker criterion.

	ACC	BE	BIM	BL	CN	ENT	INF	INT	RI
ACC	0.880								
BE	0.591	0.875							
BIM	0.531	0.6	0.825						
BL	0.478	0.563	0.812	0.89					
CN	0.796	0.672	0.559	0.497	0.891				
ENT	0.641	0.67	0.49	0.468	0.807	0.888			
INF	0.831	0.621	0.564	0.496	0.792	0.66	0.886		
INT	0.818	0.633	0.518	0.473	0.815	0.712	0.821	0.866	
RI	0.428	0.552	0.744	0.794	0.435	0.406	0.427	0.413	0.906

4.2. Structural model

The first stage in assessing the structural model entails evaluating the potential issue of multicollinearity using the variance inflation factor (VIF). In this paper, the values of VIF ranged from 1.792 to 4.217, all of which are below the recommended threshold of 5 (Hair et al., 2021). Therefore, multicollinearity does not pose a concern in this analysis.

Subsequently, the model's explanatory power was evaluated through the R-squared values, which were 0.357 for brand image, 0.519 for brand experience, 0.670 for brand loyalty, and 0.650 for repurchase intention. According to Hair et al. (2013), these R-squared values indicate a moderate level of explanatory power.

The analysis of effect sizes (f^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2) provides an important insight into the model's explanatory power. Most predictors demonstrate small effects ($f^2 < 0.15$) on their respective outcome variables (e.g. ACC, CN, ENT, INT across constructs). However, two notable exceptions emerge. Brand Image (BIM) exerts an exceptionally large influence on Brand Loyalty ($f^2 = 0.958$), while Brand Loyalty (BL) shows a very large effect on Repurchase Intention ($f^2 = 1.853$). These dominant relationships highlight their pivotal roles in the model.

Table 3. HTMT ratio.

	ACC	BE	BIM	BL	CN	ENT	INF	INT	RI
ACC									
BE	0.643								
BIM	0.582	0.657							
BL	0.524	0.611	0.821						
CN	0.834	0.729	0.611	0.543					
ENT	0.696	0.722	0.535	0.510	0.838				
INF	0.830	0.693	0.637	0.558	0.820	0.736			
INT	0.830	0.717	0.595	0.541	0.835	0.812	0.769		
RI	0.462	0.595	0.809	0.823	0.471	0.442	0.474	0.466	

Table 4. Latent variables correlations.

	ACC	BE	BIM	BL	CN	ENT	INF	INT	RI
ACC	1.000	0.592	0.531	0.477	0.796	0.641	0.828	0.818	0.433
BE	0.592	1.000	0.602	0.564	0.672	0.669	0.598	0.634	0.550
BIM	0.531	0.602	1.000	0.811	0.560	0.491	0.563	0.518	0.754
BL	0.477	0.564	0.811	1.000	0.497	0.469	0.483	0.473	0.806
CN	0.796	0.672	0.560	0.497	1.000	0.807	0.796	0.815	0.436
ENT	0.641	0.669	0.491	0.469	0.807	1.000	0.671	0.712	0.400
INF	0.828	0.598	0.563	0.483	0.796	0.671	1.000	0.871	0.423
INT	0.818	0.634	0.518	0.473	0.815	0.712	0.871	1.000	0.418
RI	0.433	0.550	0.754	0.806	0.436	0.400	0.423	0.418	1.000

The model's predictive relevance was evaluated through Q-squared values, all endogenous constructs surpass the threshold for minimal predictive power ($Q^2 > 0$). Repurchase Intention ($Q^2 = 0.506$) and Brand Loyalty ($Q^2 = 0.332$) achieve moderate-to-substantial predictive relevance, suggesting the model reliably predicts these outcomes. Brand Image ($Q^2 = 0.293$) and Brand Experience ($Q^2 = 0.207$) show weaker but acceptable predictive capacity (Hair et al., 2013). The normality of all variables was evaluated through analyses of univariate kurtosis and skewness. In accordance with established statistical thresholds, no significant deviations from normality were identified in the dataset (Hair et al., 2010). Furthermore, in testing the normality of the study, we did not include Mardia's test because PLS-SEM is a variance-based, distribution free method that does not rely on multivariate normality (Chin, 1998), and because all statistical inferences are drawn via non-parametric bootstrapping (Cheung & Lau, 2008), explicit normality testing (e.g. Mardia's test) is not required for assessing model validity in PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2019). [Appendix A](#) presents an assessment of the model's predictive power, whereas [Appendix B](#) outlines the results of the normality tests conducted on the variables.

Model fit was assessed using the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) and Unweighted Least Squares Discrepancy (d_ULS). The saturated model yielded an SRMR of 0.055, indicating excellent fit to the data (Hu & Bentler, 1999). The hypothesized (estimated) model demonstrated an SRMR of 0.074, which falls below the recommended threshold of 0.08, signifying acceptable model fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Kline, 2023). Furthermore, the estimated model of Unweighted Least Squares Discrepancy (d_ULS) yielded a d_ULS of 1.00 which is lower than the saturated model 1.658 by showing a strong fit to the data (Hair et al., 2019). This suggests that the specified paths and constructs adequately reproduce the observed covariance structure of the data. The model fit assessment is summarized in [Appendix C](#).

In this study, statistical significance is determined based on a p -value threshold of 0.05. Results with p -values less than or equal to 0.05 are considered statistically significant, indicating strong evidence against the null hypothesis. The reported p -values, along with their corresponding t -values and path coefficients, provide insights into the strength and direction of the relationships within the model. [Figure 2](#) below illustrates the structural model employed in this study, which highlights the relationships between the key variables analyzed. This model provides a visual representation of the hypothesized pathways and connections derived from the theoretical framework, serving as the foundation for our empirical analysis.

4.2.1. Direct relationship analysis

The subsequent step involves testing the study's hypotheses. Hypothesis H1a posited that information has a positive and significant effect on brand experience. The results confirmed this, showing a positive

Figure 2. Structural model.

and significant impact of information on brand experience ($\beta=0.159$, $t=2.208$, $p=0.027$), leading to the acceptance of H1a. In contrast, Hypothesis H1b suggested a positive and significant effect of accessibility on brand experience. However, the findings indicated that accessibility does not significantly influence brand experience ($\beta=0.017$, $t=0.289$, $p=0.772$), resulting in the rejection of H1b.

Hypothesis H1c proposed that customization would have a positive and significant effect on brand experience, and the results supported this hypothesis, showing a positive and significant effect of customization on brand experience ($\beta=0.170$, $t=2.277$, $p=0.023$). Therefore, H1c is accepted. Additionally, the entertainment dimension was found to have a positive and significant effect on brand experience ($\beta=0.341$, $t=5.238$, $p<0.01$), leading to the acceptance of H1d. Lastly, regarding the impact of interaction on brand experience, the study hypothesized that the interaction dimension would not have a significant effect, which was confirmed by the results ($\beta=0.108$, $t=1.296$, $p=0.195$). Hence, H1e is accepted.

Hypotheses H2a and H2c proposed a positive relationship between information, customization, and brand image. The study's findings confirmed a constructive association between information and brand image ($\beta=0.282$, $t=3.550$, $p<0.001$), as well as between customization and brand image ($\beta=0.204$, $t=2.483$, $p=0.013$). Consequently, both H2a and H2c are supported.

Hypotheses H2b, H2d, and H2e posited a positive and significant effect of accessibility, entertainment, and interaction on brand image. However, the study's results did not support these hypotheses. The relationships between accessibility and brand image ($\beta=0.091$, $t=1.330$, $p=0.184$), entertainment and brand image ($\beta=0.098$, $t=1.640$, $p=0.101$), and interaction and brand image ($\beta=-0.025$, $t=0.320$, $p=0.749$) were not statistically significant. Therefore, H2b, H2d, and H2e are not supported.

Hypotheses H3a, H3b, H3c, H3d and H3e predicted that information, accessibility, customization, entertainment, and interaction would significantly impact brand loyalty. However, the study's findings indicated that the relationships between information and brand loyalty ($\beta=-0.024$, $t=0.428$, $p=0.673$), accessibility and brand loyalty ($\beta=0.041$, $t=0.597$, $p=0.548$), customization and brand loyalty ($\beta=-0.070$, $t=1.074$, $p=0.281$), entertainment and brand loyalty ($\beta=0.073$, $t=1.542$, $p=0.124$), and interaction and brand loyalty ($\beta=0.022$, $t=0.364$, $p=0.718$) were not statistically significant. As a result, H3a, H3b, H3c, H3d, and H3e are rejected.

The study also hypothesized that brand experience would have a positive and significant impact on brand loyalty (H4). The results, however, did not support this hypothesis ($\beta=0.094$, $t=1.881$, $p=0.060$). Conversely, Hypothesis H5 predicted a positive and significant effect of brand image on brand loyalty,

Table 5. Direct relationships.

Hypothesis	B	SE	T	p values	Results
H1a: INF-> BE	0.159	0.072	2.208	0.027	Supported
H1b: ACC -> BE	0.017	0.059	0.289	0.772	Not supported
H1c: CN-> BE	0.170	0.074	2.277	0.023	Supported
H1d: ENT-> BE	0.341	0.065	5.238	0.000	Supported
H1e: INT -> BE	0.108	0.083	1.296	0.195	Supported
H2a: INF-> BIM	0.282	0.080	3.550	0.000	Supported
H2b: ACC -> BIM	0.091	0.069	1.330	0.184	Not supported
H2c: CN-> BIM	0.204	0.082	2.483	0.013	Supported
H2d: ENT-> BIM	0.098	0.060	1.640	0.101	Not supported
H2e: INT -> BIM	-0.025	0.077	0.320	0.749	Not supported
H3a: INF -> BL	-0.024	0.056	0.422	0.673	Not supported
H3b: ACC -> BL	0.041	0.069	0.601	0.548	Not supported
H3c: CN -> BL	-0.070	0.065	1.079	0.281	Not supported
H3d: ENT -> BL	0.073	0.047	1.539	0.124	Not supported
H3e: INT -> BL	0.022	0.060	0.361	0.718	Not supported
H4: BE -> BL	0.094	0.050	1.881	0.060	Not supported
H5: BIM -> BL	0.739	0.037	19.932	0.000	Supported
H6: BL -> RI	0.794	0.024	32.816	0.000	Supported

which was strongly supported by the findings ($\beta=0.739$, $t=19.932$, $p<0.001$). Therefore, H5 is accepted. Hypothesis H6, which proposed a positive and significant effect of brand loyalty on repurchase intention, was also supported by the results ($\beta=0.794$, $t=32.816$, $p<0.001$). Table 5 presents an overview of these direct relationships.

4.2.2. Mediation analysis

A mediation analysis was conducted to determine whether brand image and brand experience mediate the impact of artificial intelligence marketing efforts (information, accessibility, customization, entertainment, interaction) on brand loyalty. Hypotheses H7a and H7c proposed that brand image mediates the effect of AI marketing efforts (information, customization) on brand loyalty. The findings indicated that brand image significantly mediates the effect of information on brand loyalty ($\beta=0.209$, $t=3.548$, $p<0.001$). The total effect was also significant ($\beta=0.199$, $t=2.385$, $p=0.017$), suggesting that brand image partially mediates the relationship between information and brand loyalty. Information significantly improves Brand Image, which in turn increases Brand Loyalty. The 95% CI (0.150 to 0.268) is entirely positive, confirming a robust effect. For every 1-unit increase in INF, BL increases by 0.209 units via BIM. Therefore, H7a is supported.

For H7c, it was hypothesized that brand image mediates the effect of customization on brand loyalty. The results revealed a significant mediation effect ($\beta=0.151$, $t=2.467$, $p=0.014$). However, the total effect was not significant ($\beta=0.097$, $t=1.004$, $p=0.316$), indicating that brand image fully mediates the impact of customization on brand loyalty. Customization strengthens Brand Image, leading to higher Brand Loyalty. The 95% CI (0.090–0.241), indicating significance. A 1-unit increase in CN raises BL by 0.151 units via BIM. Thus, H7c is supported.

Hypotheses H7b, H7d, and H7e proposed that brand image mediates the effects of accessibility, entertainment, and interaction on brand loyalty. The study found no significant mediation effects for accessibility ($\beta=0.067$, $t=1.317$, $p=0.188$), entertainment ($\beta=0.072$, $t=1.634$, $p=0.102$), or interaction ($\beta = -0.018$, $t=0.320$, $p=0.749$). Consequently, H7b, H7d and H7e are not supported.

Hypotheses H8a, H8b, H8c, H8d, and H8e suggested that brand experience mediates the influence of AI marketing efforts on brand loyalty. However, the study results indicated that there is no significant mediation effect of brand experience on the relationships with information ($\beta=0.015$, $t=1.330$, $p=0.184$), accessibility ($\beta=0.002$, $t=0.263$, $p=0.793$), customization ($\beta=0.016$, $t=1.345$, $p=0.177$), entertainment ($\beta=0.032$, $t=1.798$, $p=0.072$), or interaction ($\beta=0.032$, $t=1.798$, $p=0.072$). Therefore, hypotheses H8a, H8b, H8c, H8d, and H8e are not supported. Table 6 presents an overview of these mediation analysis. For non-significant effects (95% CI includes zero), the indirect paths via Brand Image (BIM) or Brand Experience (BE) show no meaningful mediation.

Table 6. Mediation analysis.

Total effects			Direct effects			Hypothesis	Indirect effects			
Coefficient	T value	p value	Coefficient	T value	p value		Coefficient	SE	T value	p value
0.199	2.385	0.017	-0.024	0.422	0.673	H7a: INF -> BIM -> BL	0.209	0.059	3.548	0.000
0.110	1.288	0.198	0.041	0.601	0.548	H7b: ACC-> BIM -> BL	0.067	0.051	1.317	0.188
0.097	1.004	0.316	-0.070	1.079	0.281	H7c: CN-> BIM -> BL	0.151	0.061	2.467	0.014
0.178	2.572	0.010	0.073	1.539	0.124	H7d: ENT-> BIM -> BL	0.072	0.044	1.634	0.102
0.014	0.153	0.878	0.022	0.361	0.718	H7e: INT-> BIM -> BL	-0.018	0.057	0.320	0.749
						H8a: INF -> BE -> BL	0.015	0.011	1.330	0.184
						H8b: ACC -> BE -> BL	0.002	0.006	0.263	0.793
						H8c: CN-> BE -> BL	0.016	0.012	1.345	0.179
						H8d: ENT-> BE -> BL	0.032	0.018	1.798	0.072
						H8e: INT-> BE -> BL	0.010	0.011	0.943	0.346

5. Discussion and conclusion

Generation Z consumers have high expectations for brands to understand and interact with them more deeply. Duffett and Maraule (2024) suggest that businesses that incorporate emojis more frequently in their digital marketing strategies can engage more effectively with this generation. As artificial intelligence (AI) becomes more deeply embedded in brand and marketing strategies, Generation Z is anticipated to encounter AI-driven marketing applications with greater regularity during their purchasing decisions. This heightened exposure is likely to shape their perceptions and attitudes toward brands.

This paper investigates the effect of AIME on brand loyalty and repurchase intention among Generation Z consumers in Türkiye. Initially, the study examines the impact of AIME on brand experience and brand image. The findings indicate that specific artificial intelligence marketing efforts namely, information (H1a), customization (H1c), and entertainment (H1d), significantly affect brand experience. These results are similar with the research of Ho and Chow (2024), who found that information, customization, and entertainment have a substantial and notable impact on brand experience. Additionally, the paper shows that interaction is not significantly impacting brand experience, corroborating the findings of Cheng and Jiang (2022). According to Ho and Chow (2024), personalized AI marketing efforts contribute positively to the overall brand experience.

The study also explores the influence of AIME on brand image. The findings reveal that information (H2a) and customization (H2c) significantly enhance brand image, suggesting that AI-driven personalized information and customization play a key role in shaping a brand's image. Keller et al. (2011) emphasize that brand recognition, developed through consistent exposure to a company's products, fosters a lasting connection between consumers and the brand. This connection is essential for establishing brand recall, awareness, and ultimately, a strong brand image. However, the paper explores that accessibility (H2b), entertainment (H2d), and interaction (H2e) do not significantly impact brand image.

Furthermore, the paper shows no significant direct relationship between AIME and brand loyalty. This outcome stands in contrast to the findings of Kohli et al. (2023), who observed a substantial influence of AI marketing efforts on consumer preference. Likewise, Hasan et al. (2021) emphasized that AI technologies play a critical role in cultivating brand loyalty. Furthermore, the insignificant findings may be attributed to generational differences, measurement specificity, and contextual factors unique to Türkiye. Generation Z consumers, characterized by high digital literacy and low brand commitment, may respond differently to AI-driven interactions. Also, the potential measurement gap between AI marketing efforts and affective constructs like loyalty might explain the insignificance. These results suggest a need for refined theoretical modelling in future research.

The study examined the interrelationships between brand image, brand experience, and brand loyalty, providing significant insights into their dynamics among Gen Z consumers. The findings reveal that brand image has a substantial and significant positive effect on brand loyalty, consistent with prior studies (Durmaz et al., 2018). However, the analysis indicates an insignificant effect of brand experience on brand loyalty, which diverges from much of the extant literature that highlights a positive and significant relationship between the two constructs (Akoglu & Özbek, 2022).

The mixed findings in the literature regarding brand experience and its effect on brand loyalty warrant a nuanced discussion. For instance, Ong et al. (2018), explored the relationship using a

multidimensional brand experience model comprising sensory, affective, behavioral, and intellectual experiences. Their findings revealed that some dimensions, such as sensory, affective, and behavioral experiences, did not significantly impact brand loyalty, highlighting the complexity of this relationship. In contrast, other studies have reported a consistent positive association between brand experience and loyalty (Brakus et al., 2009; Ramaseshan & Stein, 2014; Reichheld & Sasser, 1990).

To contextualize these findings within the framework of this study, it is crucial to consider generational differences. Gen Z, shaped by their distinctive socio-demographic and behavioral traits, often exhibit values, preferences, and decision-making patterns that differ from those of earlier generations (Vitezić & Perić, 2021). Generational theory underscores the influence of evolving environments on generational characteristics, which may partly explain the unexpected results regarding brand experience.

Additionally, cultural factors and potential limitations in measurement tools should be explored as contributing factors. This highlights the need for future research to refine measurement tools and investigate the moderating role of cultural and generational attributes in the relationship between brand experience and brand loyalty. The study's findings suggest that while brand experience is a critical construct in loyalty models, its effect may not always be straightforward, particularly when examining specific consumer segments like Gen Z. This underscores the importance of further empirical investigations to enhance understanding of these dynamics.

The study also investigated the impact of brand loyalty on repurchase intention, revealing a robust and significant positive relationship. This finding aligns with the results of Vazifehdoost and Negahdari (2018), who demonstrated a direct effect of brand loyalty on repurchase intention.

Furthermore, a mediation analysis was conducted to assess whether brand image and brand experience mediate the effect of AIME on brand loyalty. The results show that brand image serves as a partial mediator for the impact of information on brand loyalty and acts as a full mediator for the effect of customization on brand loyalty. This suggests that more personalized messaging and products contribute to increased brand loyalty (Ho & Chow, 2024). In contrast, the study finds no substantial mediating role of brand experience in the connection between AIME and brand loyalty, which challenges the conclusions of Ho and Chow (2024), who found that brand experience mediates the link between AIME and brand preference.

In summary, this paper aims to investigate the effect of AIME on brand loyalty and repurchase intention, with a distinct emphasis on the mediating functions of brand image and brand experience. The findings show that while AIME do not have a significant direct impact on brand loyalty, factors such as information, customization, and entertainment significantly affect brand experience. Moreover, information and customization also have a significant impact on brand image. Additionally, brand image has a considerable direct impact on brand loyalty, which in turn has a strong influence on repurchase intention. Significantly, brand image mediates the relationship between information and customization and brand loyalty, while brand experience does not significantly mediate the relationship between AIME and brand loyalty.

6. Theoretical and managerial implications

This paper advances the existing body of knowledge in four distinct ways. First, it contributes to future research on the link between AIME, brand loyalty, brand experience, brand image, and repurchase intention. Second, it examines the influence of AIME on brand loyalty, with the mediation effect of brand image and brand experience, specifically within the context of Gen Z consumers. Third, the findings of this paper advance the SOR theory by considering AI marketing efforts as stimuli for brand image and brand experience, which in turn affect brand loyalty and repurchase intention. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no prior studies have examined the impact of AIME on brand loyalty while incorporating these intervening variables. Lastly, the study contributes to understanding the effect of AI marketing efforts on the behavior of Generation Z consumers. Also, this study advances the theoretical comprehension of the impact of AIME on brand loyalty within Generation Z consumers in Türkiye. By examining specific dimensions of AI marketing, such as information, customization, entertainment, and interaction, the study sheds light on their influence on brand experience and brand image, thereby enriching existing literature on AI marketing strategies. The findings challenge previous assumptions by

revealing that AI marketing efforts do not directly impact brand loyalty among Generation Z consumers. This highlights the necessity for a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing brand loyalty within the framework of AI marketing, particularly among younger consumer segments. The study underscores the mediating role of brand image in the linkage between certain dimensions of AIME (information and customization) and brand loyalty. This highlights the importance of cultivating a strong and favorable brand image through AI-driven personalized experiences to enhance brand loyalty among Generation Z consumers.

From a managerial perspective, marketers targeting Generation Z consumers in Türkiye should focus on leveraging AI technologies to deliver personalized and engaging brand experiences. Emphasizing informative, interactive, and customized content can significantly enhance brand image and foster stronger connections with this tech-savvy demographic. Given the importance of personalization, companies can utilize AI tools such as chatbots, recommendation systems, and predictive analytics to tailor marketing messages to individual preferences. For example, platforms like Salesforce Einstein, Adobe Sensei, or Google AI offer features that enable advanced audience segmentation and dynamic content personalization.

To create more customized experiences, marketers should consider using AI-driven platforms to analyze consumer data and deliver relevant, timely interactions. For instance, using AI in email marketing can help personalize product recommendations or promotional offers based on past purchases or browsing history. Similarly, social media tools powered by AI can provide insights into consumer preferences, allowing companies to develop content that resonates with Generation Z's values, such as inclusivity, sustainability, and innovation.

Additionally, the findings emphasize the necessity of integrating entertainment into AI-driven marketing efforts. Gamified experiences, augmented reality (AR), and virtual reality (VR) campaigns can engage Gen Z consumers while reinforcing a positive brand image. By aligning AI initiatives with brand identity and values, organizations can differentiate themselves and build long-term brand loyalty.

Ultimately, cultivating a strong and favorable brand image through personalized and engaging AI-driven strategies will enable companies to effectively connect with Generation Z consumers, fostering loyalty and enhancing their overall consumer experience.

7. Limitation and direction for future research

The study exhibits a range of limitations. Firstly, it focuses on evaluating the effect of AIME on brand loyalty specifically for Gen Z consumers. Future research should contemplate broadening the target population to include a more diverse sample, encompassing different age groups and demographic profiles. Secondly, this study solely relies on quantitative data. To enhance the research, future studies could incorporate qualitative data or employ mixed methods research to provide richer insights into consumer behavior and perceptions.

This research exclusively considers brand image and brand experience as intervening variables. Subsequent research should explore additional variables such as social media engagement, brand preference, trust, consumer engagement, and consumer culture, which could further elucidate the dynamics of AIME. Investigating these factors could provide a more holistic understanding of the mechanisms through which AI-driven marketing strategies influence consumer behavior, particularly in building deeper and more enduring brand connections. Additionally, the study is limited to a single country Türkiye making the findings susceptible to cultural biases. Variations in socio-cultural contexts across different countries may yield results that diverge from those obtained in this study. Future research should investigate how cultural differences influence the interplay between AIME, brand image, brand experience, and brand loyalty, potentially conducting comparative studies across multiple regions or consumer groups.

Moreover, the study's cross-sectional design captures a snapshot in time, which limits its ability to assess how the relationships among constructs evolve. Longitudinal studies are essential to explore time-dependent effects and the long-term impact of AIME on brand loyalty. While the study identifies the significant relationship between brand image and brand loyalty, it also highlights the unexpected, insignificant effect of brand experience on brand loyalty among Gen Z consumers. This finding diverges from much of the extant literature and warrants further investigation. Future research should investigate

into the nuanced relationship between brand experience and brand loyalty, examining whether specific dimensions of brand experience (e.g. sensory, affective, behavioral, or intellectual) have varying impacts on loyalty. Finally, researchers should consider generational and cultural diversity in future studies to gain a deeper understanding of how these factors moderate the effects of AIME. Such insights could help tailor AI-driven marketing strategies to align more effectively with the values, preferences, and cultural contexts of different consumer groups.

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Author contributions

CRedit: **Zakaria Abdiwali Mohamed**: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Mustafa Ünsalan**: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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About the authors

Dr. Zakaria Abdiwali Mohamed is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Management at the University of Kabridahar, Ethiopia. He holds a PhD from Nevsehir Haci Bektas Veli University, Türkiye, and his academic interests focus on the intersection of artificial intelligence, brand loyalty, and consumer behavior. Dr. Zakaria has published research on topics including indigenous conflict resolution mechanisms, culture in marketing and AI-driven marketing strategies. He has also contributed to the development of educational programs and initiatives aimed at improving the quality of education in Ethiopia. His work has been recognized for its academic rigor and cultural relevance, positioning him as an emerging scholar in the field of marketing. Dr. Zakaria is committed to advancing both research and practical solutions for sustainable development in Africa.

Dr. Mustafa Ünsalan is an Assistant Professor at Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Ankara, Türkiye. Dr. Ünsalan holds a PhD in Marketing from Marmara University. He obtained master's degree from University of New Haven, USA. He has successfully supervised and examined several master's and PhD theses. His research interests include consumer behavior, branding, digital marketing, AI in marketing, culture in marketing and PLS-SEM. He has several participations in local and international conferences.

ORCID

Zakaria Abdiwali Mohamed <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-4536-4919>
Mustafa Ünsalan <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5090-0205>

Data availability statement

Data will be available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author, Zakaria Abdiwali Mohamed (iskahay@gmail.com).

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Appendix A: Explanatory power of the model

Predictors	Variable	R square	F square	Q square			
INF	Brand Loyalty	0.670	0.005	0.332			
ACC			0.002				
CN			0.002				
ENT			0.005				
INT			0.002				
BIM			0.958				
BE	0.011	0.650	1.853	0.506			
BL	Repurchase Intention						
INF	Brand Image				0.357	0.029	0.293
ACC						0.005	
CN						0.014	
ENT						0.005	
INT			0.003	0.207			
INF	Brand Experience	0.519	0.000				
ACC			0.003				
CN			0.016				
ENT			0.081				
INT			0.009				

Appendix B: Normality test

Name	Kurtosis	Skewness
INT 1	-1.374	0.008
INT 2	-1.494	-0.063
INT 3	-1.347	0.138
INF 1	-1.474	-0.203
INF 2	-1.089	-0.692
INF 3	-1.489	-0.171
ACC 1	-1.343	-0.419
ACC 2	-1.492	-0.175
ACC 3	-1.103	-0.648
ACC 4	-1.432	-0.153
CN 1	-1.435	-0.035
CN 2	-1.495	-0.006
CN 3	-1.350	0.102
CN 4	-1.460	0.056
ENT 1	-1.480	-0.030
ENT 2	-0.812	0.716
ENT 3	-1.221	0.385
ENT 4	-1.335	0.408
BE 1	-1.418	0.143
BE 2	-1.418	0.036
BE 3	-1.499	-0.119
BE 4	-1.336	0.192
BE 5	-1.386	-0.088
BL 1	-1.399	-0.407
BL 2	-1.453	-0.114
BL 3	-1.277	0.174
BL 4	-1.468	-0.077
BIM 1	-1.556	-0.136
BIM 2	-1.296	-0.535
BIM 3	-1.368	-0.167
BIM 4	-1.428	-0.017
BIM 5	-1.417	0.030
BIM 6	-1.438	-0.107
RI 1	-1.504	-0.328
RI 2	-1.472	-0.271
RI 3	-1.469	-0.166
RI 4	-1.450	0.036
RI 5	-1.437	-0.132

Appendix C: Assessment of model fit

Model type	SRMR value	Interpretation
Saturated model	0.055	Good fit
Estimated model	0.074	Acceptable fit
Model Type	d_ULS Value	Interpretation
Saturated model	1.658	Good fit
Estimated model	1.00	Very Good fit

Appendix D: Source of measurement and items

Construct	Source	Items
Interaction	Cheng and Jiang (2022)	AI marketing efforts are sensitive to customers' needs at the moment The marketing efforts has the knowledge to answer customers' questions AI marketing efforts gives customers individual attention
Information		AI marketing efforts helps to understand events happening in the company AI marketing efforts provides recommendations on the company's products/services The AI marketing efforts provides information that helps my purchasing decisions
Accessibility		AI marketing efforts gives a more timely response AI marketing efforts are convenient and efficient AI marketing efforts can deliver efficient online assistance or information
Entertainment		AI marketing efforts can offer immediate answers anytime and anywhere It is fun and enjoyable to share a conversation with the AI marketing efforts I was absorbed in the conversation with the AI marketing efforts The conversation with the AI marketing efforts was exciting I enjoy choosing products more if they are recommended by the AI marketing efforts than if I choose them myself
Customization		I feel that using this AI and transacting with this service meets my personal needs When a customer has a problem, the AI service shows a sincere interest in solving it The AI marketing efforts are able to handle customer complaints directly and immediately I have confidence that the AI marketing efforts has the ability to get the job done
Brand Loyalty	Cheng and Jiang (2022),	I intend to keep purchasing products/services from this brand I will recommend this brand to others I will expand using other products/services of the brand I consider myself loyal to the brand
Repurchase Intention	(Ho & Chow, 2024)	I expect my relationship with this brand to continue for a long time I definitely intend to maintain my current relationship with this brand I am willing to buy more products and/or services from this brand in the future If my brand requests it, I will be willing to make further investment in supporting my brand
Brand Experience	(Ho & Chow, 2024)	I will purchase from this brand again I enjoy using AI of my brand The experience of using AI of my brand was interesting I am happy with the experience of using AI of my brand I feel happy when I do transaction via AI in my brand My brand offers 'interactive' AI process
Brand Image	(Xu et al., 2022).	This brand provides good value for money There is a reason to buy this brand instead of others This brand has personality This brand is interesting. I have a clear impression of the type of people who use this brand This brand is different from competing brands.